

TABLE 1

Solids	Calculated values for $T_{opt(F.O.A.)}$ (recorded up to the second place of decimal)	Difference between the T_{opt} values for the two approximations (recorded up to the third place of decimal)	Calcd. values for $T_{opt(S.O.A.)}$ (recorded up to the second place of decimal)	Observed value ^{2,3,4} for T_{opt}	% deviation of $T_{opt(F.O.A.)}$ value from the observed value ^{2,3,4} (recorded up to the first place of decimal)	% deviation of $T_{opt(S.O.A.)}$ value from the observed value ^{2,3,4} (recorded up to the first place of decimal)
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Silicon	22.14	2.100	24.24	25	11.44	3.0
Tin	1.97	0.045	2.01	2	1.5	0.5
Iron	14.20	0.061	14.26	15	5.3	4.9
Niobium	11.44	0.400	11.84	13	12.0	8.9
Palladium	8.54	0.018	8.56	9	5.1	4.8
Platinum	7.96	0.030	7.99	8	0.5	0.1
Osmium	15.63	0.050	15.68	20	21.9	21.6
Rhodium	16.41	0.413	16.82	18	8.8	6.5
Ruthenium	19.65	0.200	19.85	20	1.7	0.8
Thorium	7.56	0.044	7.60	8	5.5	5.0
Tungsten	8.76	0.145	8.91	10	12.4	10.9
Zinc	4.70	0.020	4.72	6	21.6	21.3
Neon	3.14	0.074	3.21	3.5	10.2	8.3
Quartz	7.75	0.027	7.78	9	14	13.5
Synthetic Sapphire	54.25	5.582	59.83	56	3.1	6.8

of phonons⁷ and phonon-phonon interaction. T_{opt} to the first order and second order of approximations are obtained as

$$T_{opt(F.O.A.)} = (\alpha/2\gamma)^{1/3} - \delta/6\gamma \quad \dots (3)$$

and

$$T_{opt(S.O.A.)} = (\alpha/2\gamma)^{1/3} \left\{ 1 + \frac{(2^{2/3} \cdot \delta^2)}{(36\alpha^{2/3} \cdot \gamma^{4/3})} \right\} - \delta/6\gamma \quad \dots (4)$$

from which we obtain

$$T_{opt(S.O.A.)} - T_{opt(F.O.A.)} = (\alpha/2\gamma)^{1/3} \left\{ \frac{(2^{2/3} \cdot \delta^2)}{(36\alpha^{2/3} \cdot \gamma^{4/3})} \right\} \quad \dots (5)$$

$T_{opt(S.O.A.)}$ value for fifteen solids of various nature has been calculated by utilizing equation (5), in combination with our results for $T_{opt(F.O.A.)}$ reported earlier¹. The values are recorded in Table I which also enlists the values for $T_{opt(F.O.A.)}$ and the differences between the said two approximations. The percentage disagreement from the observed^{2,3,4} values of the two approximations has also been recorded in the table for easy and ready reference.

Considering the reported^{2,3,4} uncertainties in the observed values of the solids, discussed in this paper, the results obtained appear to contribute fairly towards the success of the three-term-empirical equation published elsewhere¹. As expected, the $T_{opt(S.O.A.)}$ value, in general, shows an improvement over the $T_{opt(F.O.A.)}$ value, being closer to the observed value, in all cases. The synthetic sapphire is, however, an exception. This may, perhaps, be due to the probability of greater inaccuracy in the determination of its thermal conductivity in the low-temperature region.

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References

1. K. M. JHA, M. L. THAKUR and S. P. JHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 363.
2. C. Y. HO, R. W. POWELL and P. E. LILLY, "Thermal Conductivity of Elements", in *Journal of Physical and Chemical Reference Data*, (NSRDS), Washington, 1972, Vol. 1, No. 2, Reprint No. 7, 279-420.
3. M. W. ZEMANSKY, "Heat and Thermodynamics", McGraw Hill Book Company Inc., New York, London, 1957, Fourth edition, 85, 395-table 16.11.
4. C. KITTEL, "Introduction to Solid State Physics", Wiley Eastern Private Ltd., New Delhi, 1966, Third edition, 192.
5. K. M. JHA, S. P. JHA and S. N. JHA, *Indian J. Chem.* in Press.
6. K. M. JHA and M. L. THAKUR, *Indian J. Pure and Appl. Physics*, 1975, **13**, 454.
7. P. G. KLEMENS, *Proc. Phy. Soc.*, (London), 1951, **A64**, 1030.

The Kinetics of Oxidation of D (+) Glucose by Potassium bromate in Acid Medium

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THE kinetics of the oxidation of D(+)-glucose has been extensively studied using different oxidising agents, e.g., Ce(IV)¹, Cu(II)² in alkaline medium, ammoniated AgNO₃³, Pb(OAc)₄⁴, K₃Fe(CN)₆ in

aqueous NaOH⁵, potassium hexacyanoferrate⁶, K₂S₂O₈⁷, aqueous chlorine⁸, vanadium⁹, H₂O₂¹⁰, HNO₃¹¹ and KMnO₄¹². In continuation of our recent interest¹³ in oxidation of organic substrates, we now report the kinetic study of oxidation of D(+)-glucose by KBrO₃ in acid medium.

Experimental

The stock solutions of dried, at 120° for 2 hrs, KBrO₃ (Baker analysed grade) were prepared in conductivity water. D(+)-glucose, H₂SO₄ and K₂SO₄ used were of BDH, AR quality and all other chemicals used were of highest quality. The reactions were studied in a thermostat (±1°). The rate of reaction was followed by estimating residual KBrO₃ by standard iodometric method^{14,15}. The ionic strength was maintained throughout at 0.52 by adding K₂SO₄, if necessary.

The order with respect to KBrO₃ was determined by isolation method whereas in case of D(+)-glucose and H⁺ it was determined by Vant Hoff's differential method.

Observations :

TABLE 1

Concentration of reactants	Temperature 50°C	
	Mean value of K × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	Order
D(+)-glucose = 0.1000M KBrO ₃ = 0.0007M H ₂ SO ₄		
0.08783M	0.4102	2.05 } = 2
0.1094M	0.6688	
0.1318M	0.8487	
KBrO ₃ = 0.0007M H ₂ SO ₄ = 0.1706M D(+)-glucose		
0.025M	0.3146	1.2 } = 1
0.050M	0.8130	
0.1000M	1.5660	
H ₂ SO ₄ = 0.1706M D(+)-glucose = 0.1000M KBrO ₃		
0.0007M	1.566	1 } = 1
0.0005M	1.052	
0.0002M	1.493	

TABLE 2

Concentration of D(+)-glucose = 0.1000M		Temperature 50°C (Except for K ^a)			
	"	K ^b	K ^c	K ^d	K ^e
"	" KBrO ₃ = 0.0007M				
"	" H ₂ SO ₄ = 0.1706M				
K ^a *	K ^b	K ^c	K ^d	K ^e	
4.958	2.79	5.590	1.540	1.530	
6.350	4.50	9.760	1.600	1.430	
7.730	5.92	10.730	1.520	1.185	
20.470	9.60	30.970	1.590	1.034	

Effect of temperature K^a = 35°C, 40°C, 45°C and 55°C,

Effect of solvent polarity = (%H₂O-%CH₃COOH)

K^b = 95-5, 90-10, 85-15 and 80-20

Effect of high acidity K^cH₂SO₄ = 0.3282M, 0.4593M, 0.6562M and 0.9711M

Effect of ionic strength K^d(KNO₃) √μ = 0.75, 0.80, 0.85 and 0.90

K^e(K₂SO₄) √μ = " " " "

* values of rate constant are in 10³ min⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

The study of the kinetics of oxidation of D(+)-glucose has been carried out, in presence of H⁺ ions, at a constant ionic strength of 0.52, by KBrO₃. The order with respect to D(+)-glucose, H⁺ and KBrO₃ has been found to be one, two and one respectively (cf Table 1). But for a given particular concentration of H⁺ the total order of reaction gets reduced to two. The change in ionic strength, produced by KNO₃ (1-1) does not affect the rate constant. But in case of K₂SO₄ (1-2) the rate decreases as Bronsted's equation is not rigidly applicable in this case¹⁶. This independence of rate on ionic strength leads to the suggestion that at least one of the reacting species is a neutral molecule. The effect of solvent polarity (different AcOH-water mixture) shows regular increment in the rate with the increase of acetic acid to water proportion. The plot of log K and AcOH-water composition (i.e. 1/D) is linear having positive slope, thus broadly classifying bromate oxidation of D(+)-glucose as a positive ion-dipole type of reaction¹⁷. The effect of acidity dependence reveals that plot of log H⁺ and log K is linear thereby suggesting involvement of a solvent molecule in the transition state¹⁸. The plot

of $\frac{1}{K}$ vs $\frac{1}{D+(\text{glucose})}$ has been found to be linear

with a positive intercept on Y axis and thus give evidence of a complex formation between D(+)-glucose and a diprotonated bromate (H₂Br⁺O₃)¹⁹. The change in temperature on reaction rate yielded values of energy of activation, temperature coefficient, frequency factor, entropy of activation and free energy of activation as 15.74 K cal, 2.05, 1.65 × 10⁶ (sec⁻¹), -17.6 E. U. and 24.42 K cal respectively.

Thus based on above experimental findings the proposed reaction mechanism involves formation of [H₂Br⁺O₃] by the action of H₂SO₄ on KBrO₃. The diprotonated bromate ion reacts with glucose molecule to give a complex [C₆H₁₁O₆BrO₂H]⁺. This complex breaks finally to give lactone of gluconic acid in presence of a nucleophilic reagent B.

The above mentioned lactone was characterised by TLC using solvent system isopropanol-pyridine-water-acetic acid [8 : 8 : 4 : 1] as product of the reaction. The other product Br⁻ ions was tested by AgNO₃ giving characteristic pale yellow precipitate soluble in liquor ammonia.

The stoichiometry of oxidation reaction could not be established due to the fact that Br₂ was liberated at higher KBrO₃ concentration which is needed for its determination. Moreover Br₂ was liberated usually within three hours of start of reaction under normal KBrO₃ concentration at 50°. The Br⁻ formed by the reduction of BrO₃⁻ to give

Br₂ is according to the reaction

This evolution of Br₂ created complexity, which is also an oxidising agent, in the determination of the stoichiometry of the reaction.

The rate law for the reaction is represented as

$$\frac{-d}{dt} \text{Br(V)} = K_4 [\text{Br(V)}] [\text{Glucose}] [\text{H}^+]^2$$

Now for a definite H⁺ concentration, which are reproduced in the system hence act as catalyst, the rate law reduces to

$$\frac{-d}{dt} \text{Br(V)} = K_2 [\text{Br(V)}] [\text{Glucose}]$$

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References

1. R. CHARLES POTTENGER *et al*, *J. Polymer Science, Part I*, 1970, **8(2)**, 301.
2. M. P. SINGH *et al*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 537.
3. S. GHOSH and A. P. MODI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 687.
4. A. S. PERLIN, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1964, **42(ii)**, 236.
5. K. HAANEDI MALDO and SIXA VEPRREK, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1976, **41(1)**, 7-13.
6. E. L. WAKIL *et al*, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1976, **41(1)**, 14-18.
7. S. P. SRIVASTAVA and G. B. PUROHIT, *Vijnan Parishad Anusandhan Patrika*, 1971, **4**, 199-210.
8. A. E. BERNARDELLI, *Tr. Leningrad, Tekhnol. Inst. Tsellyul Bum Prom*, 1968, No. 21, 1864-7.
9. P. M. PATHAK and M. P. SINGH, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India, Sec. (A)*, 1969, **39 Pt. (2)**, 185.
10. N. R. DHAR, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1947, **16A**, 14-19.
11. KOPRIVA BEDRICH, *Listy Cuprov*, 1967, **83(2)**, 36-9.
12. B. V. TRONOV and D. STATEI, *Esengalov Molodykh uch*, 1965, 17-13.
13. S. N. SHUKLA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 2249.
14. F. H. WESTHEIMER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1940, **17**, 61.
15. A. G. CHATTERJEE and V. AWASTHI, *Z. Phys.*, 1940, **16**, 61.
16. BRONSTED, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1922, **102**, 169.
17. E. S. AMISS, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1953, **30**, 351.
18. LONG and PAUL, *Chem. Revs.*, 1957, 935.
19. H. WILLIAM RICHARDSON, "Oxidation in Organic Chemistry", edited by K. B. WIBERG, 1965, 247.

Effect of Halide Ions on Cathodic Polarization of Nickel in Presence of Dicyandiamide and Related Compounds in Sulphuric Acid

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THE synergistic effect of anions and amines in corrosion inhibition of iron in acid solution has been investigated by a number of workers¹⁻⁴. Also the adsorption of anions on metal surfaces has been investigated by different investigators⁵⁻⁹. However, such investigations on the effects of halides on the corrosion of nickel in acid solution are recent and rare¹⁰⁻¹². The present investigation is concerned with the effect of halides on cathodic polarization of nickel in deaerated 1N sulphuric acid in presence of dicyandiamide, biguanide and guanyl urea.

Experimental

Nickel (99.9% purity) used as electrode, was in the form of beads of circular surface area 0.2 sq. cm. The galvanostatic method used for steady state polarization studies consisted of a constant current generator and one vernier potentiometer having different channels for measuring corrosion current and corrosion potential. All experiments were carried out at 25 ± 1° in inert atmosphere. A saturated calomel electrode was used as reference electrode.

Results and Discussion

The results of the polarization measurements are generally interpreted in terms of Tafel parameters. The E_{corr}, cathodic Tafel slopes, exchange current densities (obtained by extrapolation method) have been tabulated in Table 1. It can be seen that the open circuit corrosion potential is gradually shifted from 232 mv (vs SCE) in pure sulphuric acid to 246 mv, 370 mv and 416 mv with the addition of chloride, bromide and iodide ions respectively. The open circuit corrosion potentials of nickel in sulphuric acid is 232 mv (vs SCE) and the addition of dicyandiamide, guanyl urea and biguanide shifts it to 216 mv, 217 mv and 242 mv. The corresponding changes of Tafel slopes are, however, not so marked in presence of organic compounds. The effect of halides on the exchange current densities is also quite apparent from the Table 1.

In presence of chloride ions, dicyandiamide and guanyl urea shift the open circuit potential to more negative direction but this shift is not so prominent in case of biguanide. Dicyandiamide and guanyl urea shift open circuit potential towards positive direction as compared to the solutions containing